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THE PATTERNS OF DEPOPULATION IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA: SPATIAL AUTOCORRELATION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The patterns of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Spatial autocorrelation analysis

Depopulation is one of the key contemporary demographic challenges for Bosnia and Herzegovina. Adverse demographic trends are causing various problems for Bosnian society and its economy, affecting the national and local labor markets, the public pension system, education, the public health system, etc. Therefore, the purpose of this research is to analyze the spatial patterns of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina in order to identify the areas of the country that are particularly vulnerable to negative demographic trends and to identify the factors that may be contributing to these trends. A geospatial analysis of depopulation was carried out by using global and local indices of spatial autocorrelation. To identify spatial patterns of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the study used the data on the total population change, natural population change, the vital index, the ageing index, and the ageing coefficient for the period 2013-2021 at the municipal level. The findings of this study can serve as a basis for future demographic research and the demographic development of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

KEY WORDS

spatial analysis, spatial autocorrelation, demographic trends, depopulation, Bosnia and Herzegovina

1. Introduction

Population decline is one of the key issues facing many developed but also developing countries in the world. This demographic process causes many challenges for societies all over the world. Depopulation affects the economy, national and local global labor markets, education and health systems, etc. Previous research on depopulation processes in the world indicates that Europe is facing intensive population decline (Newsham and Rowe, 2022), and especially in countries in Southern and Eastern Europe (Pantić, 2019). However, depopulation is a demographic process characterized by spatial or territorial disparities (González-Leonardo et al., 2023). Depopulation varies across the area of a country and is more common in peripheral rural areas (González-Leonardo et al., 2023; Johnson and Lichter, 2019; Viñas, 2019). However, it can also affect urban regions in countries with intensive emigration across national borders (Bērziņš and Zvidriņš, 2011). Therefore, some studies showed population increases in certain rural areas, and decreases in certain urban areas (Newsham and Rowe, 2022).

Since many countries in the world are facing population decline, numerous studies that cover the issue of population decline have been conducted in recent years. For example, Benassi et al. (2023) and Reynaud & Miccoli (2018) investigated the effects and determinants of population changes in Italy, Gil-Alonso et al. (2023) and González-Leonardo et al. (2023) characteristics of depopulation processes in Spain, Truskolaski and Bugowski (2022) determinants and causes of depopulation in Eastern and Central Europe, Czibere et al. (2021) trends and causes of depopulation in Hungary and Poland, Živanović et al. (2022) and Pantić (2019) characteristics of population change in Serbia, Čipin and Ilieva (2017) population decline in Croatia and Bulgaria, etc.

Bosnia and Herzegovina, as a south European country, is not an exception in terms of depopulation processes. This country has been facing negative demographic trends since the end of the 20th century, but these unfavorable trends were deepened by war in the period 1992-1995, as well as post-war emigration flows and the related decline in population biodynamics. Many recent studies in this country treated the subject of depopulation and confirmed adverse trends for various demographic indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Gekić et al., 2020; Pobrić and Robinson, 2015). Gekić et al. (2020) point out that depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina is mostly caused by intensive emigration to foreign countries, decreasing biodynamics of the Bosnian population, and population ageing. According to Pobrić and Robinson (2015) Bosnia and Herzegovina faced a decrease in the proportion of the young

population and an increase of the old population. Moreover, population ageing and a decline in fertility rates have been accompanied by emigration of the reproductive and working-age population. In demographic analysis and the analysis of spatial differences in the level and causes of demographic changes and depopulation, methods of spatial analysis are especially important. According to Matthews and Parker (2013) there has been a rise in interest in spatial demography, which is caused by improvements in new technologies and new methods of analysis.

In recent years, many demographic studies have been performed using spatial analysis methods. For example, Benassi et al. (2023) used spatial analysis to determine spatial dimensions and local heterogeneities of population decline in municipalities in Italy, Szymanowski and Latocha (2021) used methods of spatial analysis to determine spatial relationships between environmental factors and depopulation rates in the Kłodzko region of Poland, Nieto Masot et al. (2020) applied methods of spatial analysis to determine rural-urban structure of Spanish municipalities. Among spatial analysis techniques, a spatial autocorrelation analysis has been applied in various cases. Spatial autocorrelation methods can be used to determine how similar or different variables are in adjacent locations. Global statistical indices can be used to analyze spatial autocorrelation through an entire dataset or statistical sequence. Local statistical indices of spatial autocorrelation can be used to identify hot and cold spot areas (Anselin, 1995; Ord and Getis 1995; Anselin and Getis, 1992). Many studies have been conducted in recent years based on the use of the spatial autocorrelation method.

For example, Aoki (2022) applied the spatial autocorrelation method to examine the spatial distribution of low-density demographic areas caused by the excess outflow of younger generations and to estimate aggregation and decentralization of subregions with significant population decline in Japan. Kurek et al. (2022) used spatial autocorrelation to identify demographic patterns of functional urban areas in Poland, and Novoseltseva et al. (2019) applied spatial autocorrelation to analyse demographic situation in 34 municipal formations in the Kemerovo Region of the Russian Federation, etc. Several studies have been performed on the application of spatial analysis and spatial autocorrelation analysis to various demographic variables in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Mijić and Ateljević (2018) studied the use of contemporary GIS software in demographic research of the Bosnian entity of the Republic of Srpska. Kadušić et al. (2023a) performed spatial autocorrelation analysis of mortality rates in Bosnia and Herzegovina, while Kadušić et al. (2023b) conducted a study on spatial patterns of population ageing in Bosnia and Herzegovina with the application of spatial autocorrelation analysis.

The aim of this research is to determine if demographic processes in Bosnia and Herzegovina are affected by spatial autocorrelation, if there are areas in Bosnia and Herzegovina that are particularly vulnerable to negative demographic trends, which areas and municipalities are facing the highest level of depopulation and adverse demographic trends, what are the potential causes of the current spatial distribution of demographic processes, and what are the next steps in spatial demographic research in this country.

2. Methodology

In this study, a spatial analysis of basic demographic indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina was performed using spatial autocorrelation methods in order to identify spatial clusters with high or low values. Spatial autocorrelation methods demonstrate how similar or different variables are in adjacent locations, and determine the correlation within variables across space (Getis, 2008; Getis, 2007). Global statistical indices are used to analyze spatial autocorrelation through an entire dataset or statistical sequence, while local statistical indices of spatial autocorrelation identify hot and cold spot areas (Anselin, 1995; Ord and Getis 1995; Anselin and Getis, 1992). Therefore, global statistical indices (Global Moran's I and Getis-Ord General G) and local statistical indices (Anselin Local Moran's I and Local Getis-Ord G_i^*) were used to determine the spatial distribution of basic demographic indicators, that is, whether certain demographic variables are clustered or dispersed in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Special attention should be given to the process of collecting statistical data in Bosnia and Herzegovina and why this process significantly challenges demographic research in this country. Demographic studies in Bosnia and Herzegovina performed at the municipal level mostly contain data for basic demographic indicators. The main reason for this is that only one population census in Bosnia and Herzegovina was conducted after the war (in 2013). The administrative division of Bosnia and Herzegovina led to the existence of several institutes for statistics in this country. Unfortunately, there is a lack of effective coordination between these institutions and, in some cases, they apply different methodologies for collecting and publishing certain statistical data. Consequently, it is very challenging to perform any detailed demographic analysis at the municipal level, which is a prerequisite for spatial analysis, and therefore get useful results that could be used in the demographic development of the country. However, since the 2013 population census, it is possible to track and analyze more specific demographic indicators, which allows us to comprehend the level of demographic changes in Bosnia and Herzegovina in recent years.

In this study, publications, bulletins, and sources from several institutions that track demographic statistics in Bosnia and Herzegovina were used. Those are the Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BHAS), Institute for Statistics of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FZS), Republic of Srpska Institute of Statistics (RZSRS), Federal Employment Institute in Sarajevo (FZZZ) and the Employment Institute of the Republic of Srpska in Banja Luka (ZZRS). Therefore, demographic and socio-economic indicators at the municipal level in the period 2013-2021 were used to determine the level of demographic changes, the extent of depopulation, and which areas were the most affected by adverse demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Total population change, natural population change, vital index, ageing coefficient, and ageing index are used as demographic indicators of depopulation. Whereas, socio-economic indicators used in the analysis are average net wage, unemployment rate, unemployment rate change, unemployment of the population with a university degree, high-school education and unemployment of qualified workers, emigration rate, and net migration rate. Unfortunately, the Republic of Srpska does not track emigration abroad. Therefore, this indicator was possible to analyze only at the level of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Table 1).

Table 1. Basic demographic and socio-economic indicators of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Demographic indicators	Socio-economic indicators
Total population change	Average net wage
Natural population change	Unemployment rate and unemployment rate change
Vital index	Unemployment rate of the population with a university degree, high school education, and unemployment of qualified workers
Ageing coefficient	
Ageing index	Migration balance

In order to determine the correlation between demographic and socio-economic indicators of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the nonparametric method of Spearman’s Rank-Order Correlation was used. GIS queries were used to detect which municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina have negative values for a large number of indicators and are faced with the most adverse demographic trends or depopulation.

3. Results and Discussion

P-value of 0.000 for Global Moran’s *I* for all demographic indicators implies that the null hypothesis is rejected and that the spatial distribution of high and/or low values in the observed statistical dataset of total population change rate, natural population change, ageing coefficient, ageing index, and vital index in Bosnia and Herzegovina is more clustered than would be expected in random spatial processes. Further, given a *z*-score greater than of 3.561, there is less than a 1.0% probability that this spatial distribution of demographic indicators could be the result of chance. Therefore, Global Moran’s *I* and Getis Ord General *G* confirmed the clustering of depopulation indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina. For datasets with negative values, only global Moran’s *I* was determined since Global Getis-Ord cannot be determined for negative values (Table 2).

Table 2. Global Moran’s *I* and Getis-Ord General *G* values for basic demographic indicators of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021.

Indicator	Global Moran’s <i>I</i>			Getis-Ord General <i>G</i>		
	Index	<i>z</i> -score	<i>p</i> -value	Index	<i>z</i> -score	<i>p</i> -value
Pop. Change	0.166	3.759	0.00	-	-	-
Natural Pop. Change	0.267	5.443	0.00	-	-	-
Ageing Coeff.	0.298	6.131	0.00	0.007	2.499	0.01
Ageing Index	0.157	3.561	0.00	0.007	1.286	0.19
Vital Index	0.352	7.114	0.00	0.007	5.004	0.00

Source: Author’s calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022)

The local statistical indices, Anselin Local Moran’s *I* and Getis Ord *G*^{*}, enabled the identification or existence of spatial clusters with high or low values of population change, natural population change, ageing coefficient, ageing index, and vital index in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The statistical significance of local indices is based on the ratio of the *z*-score and *p*-value at the 0.05 significance level. Anselin Local Moran’s *I* values for basic demographic variables presented in Table 2. indicate moderate positive spatial autocorrelation and the clustering of high and low values of observed demographic indicators. Moreover, positive autocorrelation suggests that values in one geographic area are similar to the values in neighbouring areas (Tab. 2). The Getis-Ord *G*^{*} Index was used to identify high-risk and low-risk areas of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The *G*^{*} was calculated for each data point in the observed demographic datasets. Hot spots with 99% and 95% confidence intervals were identified (Figures 1 to 5).

Figure 1: Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G* analysis of Population Change in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022).

Figure 2: Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G* analysis of Natural Population Change in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022).

Figure 3: Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G* analysis of Ageing Coefficient in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022).

The evidence of spatial patterns in the data is visible in the presented maps since both local indices of spatial autocorrelation indicate the same patterns in similar geographical areas. In other words, since both Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G* analyses indicate the presence of a hotspot of high values in a particular region, this suggests that the region is truly a hotspot and not simply the result of chance.

Figure 4: Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G* analysis of Ageing Index in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021. Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022).

Figure 5: Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G* analysis of Vital Index in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022).

The method of spatial autocorrelation analysis, in addition to pointing out the clustered areas that are facing adverse demographic trends, made it possible to identify the municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina that are particularly affected by depopulation. Namely, based on the value of selected demographic indicators and the number of times they appear in hot spot areas, several municipalities are particularly threatened with depopulation processes. Municipalities that appear in all or most of the clusters with high values can be characterized as municipalities with a high degree of depopulation risk. These are the municipalities of Foča (RS) and Foča (FBiH), Istočni Drvar, Glamoč, Ribnik, Petrovac and Novi Grad. On the other hand, the analysis also pointed to areas and municipalities that, at the level of Bosnia and Herzegovina, are currently recording more positive demographic trends, such as Novi Grad Sarajevo, Novo Sarajevo, Ilidža, Kiseljak, Bužim, Velika Kladuša, Cazin, Zenica, Visoko, Novi Travnik, Zavidovići, etc.

The factors influencing these spatial demographic processes in Bosnia and Herzegovina are very complex. The majority of authors investigating the demographic trends of Bosnia and Herzegovina singled out physical-geographical, political, and socio-economic factors as the main causes of negative demographic processes in this country (Kadušić et al., 2023a; Gekić et al., 2020; Pabrić, Robinson, 2015). The identified spatial clusters are areas that

were less populated parts of pre-war Bosnia and Herzegovina due to less favorable geographical features. According to Nurković (2018) and Nurković and Drešković (2013), unequal regional development and the lagging of rural areas in the second half of the 20th century in this country were a consequence of the polarization of economic activities. Depopulation of rural areas in the pre-war period was caused by planned industrial development in urban areas that attracted rural population. These unfavourable development processes in rural areas were most noticeable in negative demographic trends and depopulation. However, political factors deepened these adverse demographic processes in the mentioned areas. The Dayton Peace Agreement and the entity line, which led to the division of certain pre-war municipalities, deepened the unfavorable social conditions of settlement in this area, leading to emigration and negative demographic trends (Kadušić et al., 2023a).

Therefore, rural municipalities along the entity boundary line between administrative units of Bosnia and Herzegovina, and municipalities that were divided by the entity boundary, are particularly affected by unfavorable demographic trends. Due to adverse socio-economic and political circumstances, these municipalities are losing some of their population. Socio-economic factors such as lower living standards and poorer living conditions, high unemployment rates, etc. contributed to the negative demographic processes. However, it should be emphasized that there are regional differences in the economic and demographic trends of the inter-entity municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Thus, along the entity line, municipalities that are considered to be economically more developed parts of this country and municipalities with more favorable demographic trends are also situated (for example, municipalities Tešanj, Usora, Teslić, Dobož, Dobož-Jug, Dobož-Istok, etc.). This indicates the complexity of the factors that influence spatial demographic processes in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In order to determine the causes of depopulation and quantify the influence of these causes on demographic trends in the municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina, a preliminary correlation analysis was performed between the socio-economic and demographic indicators of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Non-parametric correlation analysis confirmed the relationship between several demographic and socio-economic indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina. As presented in Table 3, correlation analysis confirmed a positive correlation coefficient between population change and migration balance (0.736), rate of unemployment change and population change rate (0.335), unemployment rate of the population with a university degree and migration balance (0.320), and a

negative correlation coefficient between emigration rate and population change (-0.285). These results indicate influence of the unemployment rate on emigration (especially the emigration of individuals with university degrees) and the influence of the unemployment rate and migration on population change in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Table 3. Non-parametric correlation analysis of total population change and socio-economic indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013-2021.

Variable	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
A	1.000	.138	.335**	.323**	.128	.077	.087	.736**
	.	.100	.000	.000	.135	.373	.312	.011
B	.138	1.000	.303**	.287**	.326**	.048	-.316**	.006
	.100	.	.000	.001	.000	.577	.000	.961
C	.335**	.303**	1.000	.995**	.231**	.277**	.167	.232*
	.000	.000	.	.000	.007	.001	.052	.039
D	.323**	.287**	.995**	1.000	.235**	.289**	.179*	.232*
	.000	.001	.000	.	.006	.001	.036	.039
E	.128	.326**	.231**	.235**	1.000	.638**	.172*	.320**
	.135	.000	.007	.006	.	.000	.044	.000
F	.077	.048	.277**	.289**	.638**	1.000	.650**	.135
	.373	.577	.001	.001	.000	.	.000	.234
G	.087	-.316**	.167	.179*	.172*	.650**	1.000	.036
	.312	.000	.052	.036	.044	.000	.	.752
H	.736**	.006	.232*	.232*	.320**	.135	.036	1.000
	.000	.961	.039	.039	.000	.234	.752	.

A. Population Change; B. Net Wage; C. Unemployment Change; D. Rate of Unemployment Change; E. Unemployment of the population with a University Degree; F. Unemployment of the population with a High School Education; G. Unemployment rate of Qualified Workforce; H. Migration balance (Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina)

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author’s calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2022)

Global and local indices of spatial autocorrelation analysis are very useful tools in the analysis of regional disparities in depopulation (Alamá-Sabater et al., 2019). However, spatial autocorrelation analysis can identify spatial patterns, but it cannot determine their causes, it depends on the scale at which spatial data is aggregated, it assumes spatial homogeneity, meaning that the relationships between variables are consistent across space, relies on the availability and quality of spatial data, gives better results with bigger samples or larger statistical

datasets (Getis, 2008; Chi, Zhu, 2008). Despite mentioned disadvantages, in this study spatial autocorrelation analysis provided identification of areas with similar demographic trends and spatial patterns, determined the distribution of demographic changes or depopulation, highlighted spatial inequalities in demographic variables and provided valuable information for future demographic research. Since the spatial autocorrelation analysis points out where the clustering or dispersion of the data is happening but does not explain the causes of spatial differentiation of the data, future research should include the application of additional methods, such as spatial regression modelling, in order to identify the casual relationship between demographic variables and economic, political and social processes in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Nonetheless, spatial autocorrelation analysis allowed us to determine the distribution of demographic indicators of depopulation and identify areas with similar demographic trends and areas with spatial inequalities in demographic development. Understanding the spatial patterns and their causes can help policymakers develop policies and activities that address specific demographic challenges in different regions of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Identification of areas that are more vulnerable to depopulation can guide the development of strategies to attract or retain population in those areas.

4. Conclusion

Spatial autocorrelation analysis was performed in order to identify the spatial distribution of demographic indicators of depopulation, areas with similar demographic trends, and regional disparities in demographic development in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Global Moran's I and Getis-Ord General G, and Anselin Local Moran's I and Getis-Ord G^* indices, a low p -value, and a high z -score for statistical datasets of population change, natural population change, ageing coefficient, ageing index, and vital index, suggest moderate spatial autocorrelation and the spatial clustering of data.

Global statistical indices indicate a moderate positive autocorrelation, while local statistical indices indicate a clustering of data for basic demographic indicators in certain areas of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The results of spatial autocorrelation analysis have been used to determine clustered areas and municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina that are particularly affected by depopulation. Based on the value of selected demographic indicators and the number of times each municipality appears in hotspot areas, several municipalities are particularly threatened by depopulation processes. Therefore, municipalities with a high degree of risk of depopulation are Foča (RS), Foča

(FBiH), Istočni Drvar, Glamoč, Ribnik, Petrovac and Novi Grad. On the other hand, municipalities with more positive demographic trends are, for example, Novi Grad Sarajevo, Novo Sarajevo, Ilidža, Kiseljak, Bužim, Velika Kladuša, Cazin, Zenica, Visoko, Novi Travnik, Zavidovići, etc.

Spatial disparities in demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina are a consequence of social, economic, political, and other factors. Adverse social, economic, and political issues are particularly prominent in rural municipalities that are situated along the boundary of administrative entities in Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, research suggests that there is an exception to this trend, and some developed municipalities are also situated along the entity boundary. This confirms the complexity of the factors influencing spatial demographic development in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The main contribution of this research is the identification of clustered areas and municipalities with adverse demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and therefore the results of the study can be used for future research on factors that are causing spatial demographic disparities. However, although very useful in determining the spatial distribution of demographic values in the researched area, spatial autocorrelation analysis cannot determine the factors influencing the clustering of the data. Since the relationship between variables usually varies across space, future analysis should include methods like spatial regression modelling, which could help in identifying the main factors of spatial depopulation disparities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

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